

DIPOLE MOMENTS OF METALLIC SOAPS

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The dipole moments of six metallic soaps, viz., the oleates of Zn, Cu, Mg, Ni, Pb and Ca have been determined by a heterodyne beat method. The values are 0.29 D, 1.20 D, 1.66 D, 2.67 D, 4.29 D and 1.49 D respectively.

Though the metallic soaps are generally regarded as non-polar from their physico-chemical, particularly solubility behaviour, being highly soluble in organic solvents, these data show them (except Zn) to be fairly highly polar. It is suggested that this high polarity is caused not by a high charge but by a comparatively large separation between the charges owing to the centre of negative charge residing well within the hydrocarbon radical of the oleate.

It is further observed from an examination of the μ -values of the group II elements, Mg, Ca and Zn oleates that the order of their dipole moments is opposite to the order of their ionisation potentials.

Calculation of μ -values has also been made according to a new equation developed by Jathar, Sathe and Iyengar. It is found that μ (Jathar *et. al.*) is always lower than μ (Debye). It is further observed that P_2 (total polarisation) is strongly dependent on concentration both in the new and in the classical Debye equation and so the new equation does not offer any advantage over the Debye equation in these cases.

Attempts have also been made to treat the data by a recently developed simpler method of calculation due to Guggenheim. The method seems to be generally applicable and the μ -values are in fair agreement with Debye values.

The metallic salts of long chain fatty acids, which are generally called metallic soaps, have got important applications in industry (vide Elliott, "The Alkaline Earth and Heavy Metal Soaps", Reinhold Publ. Corp., 1946). They are generally used in the manufacture of lubricating grease, waterproofs, driers in paints and varnishes and in various other industrial products (for review vide Lesser, *Soap & Sanitary Chem.*, 1945, 21, 36, 40).

In spite of extensive technical use very few systematic scientific data exist about them, though they are of undoubted interest not only owing to their peculiar physical and chemical properties but also due to their rather unusual type of chemical structure. Great interest has recently been shown about the physico-chemical properties of some of these soaps, particularly their behaviour against organic solvents (Martin and Pink, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1750; Gray and Alexander, *J. Phys. Coll.-Chem.*, 1949, 53, 23) and their X-ray structure (Marsden *et al.*, *J. Amer. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 25, 454; Vold, Hattiangdi and Vold, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1949, 4, 93).

As opposed to the true soaps quite a few metallic soaps dissolve in pure aromatic and chlorinated hydrocarbons and often dissolve better in mixed solvents (Matiollo, "Protective and Decorative Coatings", John Wiley, 1942, Vol. II, p. 621; Palit, *J. Amer. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 190; Crawford, *Nature*, 1947, 160, 19) and so they are generally regarded as non-polar though no adequate evidence exists to this

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point. It was hence thought of interest to carry out measurements of the dielectric constant and dipole moment of these substances, and these data are expected to throw some light on their molecular structure, which in its turn would enable us to explain their properties. This paper reports our results of measurement of dielectric constant and dipole moment of oleates of six bivalent metals, viz., Ca, Mg, Zn, Cu, Ni and Pb by the heterodyne beat method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation.—The usual method of double decomposition between dilute solution of Na-oleate and a slight excess of metallic salts was adopted in the preparation of metallic oleates. The sodium oleate was dissolved in aqueous butyl alcohol and the metallic salt e.g., acetate (Ca and Pb) or sulphate (Mg, Ni, Zn, Cu) was in pure aqueous solution. The oleates, thus obtained, were washed repeatedly with warm water until completely free from soluble impurities. The product was finally dried in a vacuum oven at 50° .

Solvents.—Benzene (C. P.) was twice distilled over drierite (CaSO_4) in an all-glass apparatus. The solvent, thus obtained, was dried over sodium.

Apparatus.—The heterodyne beat apparatus used in our measurements has been designed and constructed in our laboratory by simplification and modification of a circuit used by Stranathan (*Rev. Sci. Instr.*, 1934, 5, 334; Terman, "Radio Engineering", McGraw Hill, 1947). Two identical oscillators of Hartley type were used. One of the oscillators was kept at a constant frequency and the standardised capacity in the other was varied. In order to overcome the difficulty of frequency drifts in oscillators, the plate voltage was supplied from a dry cell, whereas the filament was heated by a 6-volt storage battery. A variable air condenser provided with a slow motion scale and cali-

Fig. 1

brated against a standard capacitor of a Q-meter in the 400-1000 kilocycle range was used as the standard capacity in our measurement. The beat was detected by a straight receiver provided with a tuning magic eye. The latter device was found to be highly sensitive because even when our ears failed to discriminate extremely low frequency beats, fluttering of the magic eye aided in the accurate adjusting of the variable standardised capacitor against which measurement was made by substitution method. The circuit diagram of the oscillator is shown above.

The measurements were made at room temperature. For this purpose an oil-bath thermostat containing an oil of low dielectric constant was used.

Experimental Cell.—The cell was designed in accordance with the directions given by Sauce and Briscoe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 315) and modified by Le Fevre and Russel (Le Fevre, "Dipole Moments," Methuen Series, 2nd edition, revised and reset 1948, p. 35; Le Fevre and Russel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 491). As regards the silvering of the cell the standard method of reducing ammoniacal silver nitrate by glucose solution was adopted in our case.

Density Measurement.—Density of each concentration of the experimental solution was measured by a specific gravity bottle.

Refractive Index Measurement.—As the molar refraction of the metallic salts of fatty acids is neither known nor calculable from the standard atomic refraction table, it is found advisable to measure the refractive index for each concentration and then to compute the final result from the following formula:—

$$R_2 = \frac{R_{12} - f_1 R_1}{f_2} = \text{molar refraction for a single solute molecule,}$$

$$\text{where } R_{12} = \frac{n_{12}^2 - 1}{n_{12}^2 + 2} \times \frac{f_1 M_1 + f_2 M_2}{d_{12}} = \text{molar refraction of each solution,}$$

n_{12} = refractive index for Na_D lines of each solution; f_1 = mol. fraction of the solvent; d_{12} = density of solutions; f_2 = mol. fraction of the solute;

$$R_1 = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 - 2} \times \frac{M_1}{d} = \text{molar refraction of benzene,}$$

n = refractive index of benzene, d = density of benzene, M_1 = molecular weight of benzene, M_2 = molecular weight of the solute used.

In this case it is tacitly assumed that the mixture law is obeyed in the case of molar refraction.

Method of Calculations.—If a polar substance is dissolved in a non-polar solvent and the solution is so dilute as to show negligible solvent-solute interaction, the polarisation for that solution is given by

$$P_{12} = \frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon + 2} \times \frac{f_1 M_1 + f_2 M_2}{d_{12}}$$

where ϵ is the dielectric constant of that solution.

If P_1 be the polarisation of the solvent, then assuming the mixture law, the polarisation $P_{12} = f_1 P_1 + f_2 P_2$, where P_2 is the polarisation of the solute.

$$\text{Now } P_2 = \frac{P_{12} - f_1 P_1}{f_2}$$

is plotted against f_2 and the polarisation for the single solute molecule corresponding to infinite dilution, *i.e.*, $f_2 = 0$ is taken for the calculation of dipole moment because it is at $f_2 = 0$ that the solute-solute interaction vanishes. The orientation polarisation $P_{2(\text{orient})}$ is obtained by subtracting R_2 from P_2 . No correction was made for atomic polarisation, as the samples used were not considered to be of such high order of purity as to merit such accurate treatment.

Thus $\mu = 0.0127 \sqrt{P_{2(\text{orient})} T} \times 10^{-18}$, where T = absolute temperature of the bath.

Dielectric Constant Measurement.—Dielectric constant was measured by the substitution method. To start with, one of the oscillators was kept fixed and the other was varied by varying the auxiliary as well as the standard capacitor till the beat was zero. This was taken as the initial reading. The experimental cell filled with air was next connected in parallel with the standardised condenser which was adjusted till the beat was just zero. The difference in the two readings give us the capacity due to the cell. The initial reading without the cell, the reading when the cell was filled with air and also the reading with the cell first filled with benzene and then with the experimental solution—these four readings were taken. The dielectric constant for the particular solution was then calculated with the help of the following equation,

$$\epsilon = 2.270 \times \frac{C_{\text{soln}} - C_0}{C_{\text{benzene}} - C_0} = \frac{2.270 \times C_{\text{air}} - C_{\text{benzene}}}{1.270}$$

where C_{soln} = capacity of the cell with the interspace filled with dielectric solution; C_{benzene} = capacity of the cell filled with benzene and C_0 = zero capacity *i.e.*, capacity of leads, etc.

The dielectric constant of benzene was taken as 2.270 for our measurement. All the data for dielectric constant measurements were taken at a fixed frequency of 600 k. cycles. sec^{-1} .

DISCUSSION

The results of our measurements are presented in Table I. All the metallic soaps studied are observed to have dipole moments which range from almost zero to as high as 4.5×10^{-18} . Of the three second group elements, magnesium, calcium and zinc, it is observed that zinc, which is the highest member of the series, has got the lowest (almost zero) dipole moment. This is probably expected, as the general trend, when we go down the periodic table is to form non-polar bonds with organic radicals, which is particularly true of metals of sub-group B. In agreement with the above idea, magnesium, which like zinc easily forms covalent organometallic compounds, *e.g.* Grignard reagents, is found to have low dipole moment, much lower than that of calcium. In order to test if the dipole moment is determined by the position in the periodic table, we attempted to determine the dipole moment of beryllium and barium

TABLE I

Temperature = 30°.

Sample.	f_3 .	ϵ .	n_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_{12} .	P_3 in c.c.	P_2 .	R_{12} .	R_2 in c.c.	R_3 mean.	μ_3 .
Zinc oleate	.00106	2.2770	1.4948	.8658	27.29	242.7		26.65	180.95		
	.00151	2.2735	1.4946	.8654	27.14	245.2	1862c.c	26.62	188.90	184.42	0.29D
	.00120	2.2720	1.4950	.8650	27.07	216.7		26.57	200.00		
Copper oleate	.00363	2.2840	1.4947	.8672	27.66	250.8		26.89	181.2		
	.00257	2.2780	1.4948	.8662	27.39	237.0	215c.c	26.73	182.9	185.5	1.2D
	.00213	2.2740	1.4949	.8654	27.28	230.0		26.68	192.50		
	.00128	2.2720	1.4950	.8650	27.00	219.0		26.55	203.10		
Nickel oleate	.00301	2.3170	1.4936	.8656	28.06	428.6		26.76	182.70		
	.00223	2.2950	1.4937	.8650	27.62	372.2	328c.c.	26.25	188.30	182.6	2.67D
	.00153	2.2854	1.4938	.8648	27.33	346.4		26.53	183.00		
	.00102	2.2787	1.4939	.8646	27.16	333.3		26.44	176.50		
Magnesium oleate	.00302	2.2910	1.4946	.8650	27.67	298.0		26.80	182.32		
	.00198	2.2800	1.4947	.8648	27.33	272.7	246c.c	26.63	181.82	187.62	1.66D
	.00138	2.2760	1.4948	.8646	27.16	253.7		26.55	188.41		
	.00096	2.2730	1.4949	.8644	27.06	250.0		26.49	197.92		
Calcium oleate	.00376	2.3360	1.4947	.8660	28.45	452.0		26.92	183.6		
	.00268	2.3260	1.4948	.8654	28.12	504.0	600c.c	26.74	182.8	187.7	4.49D
	.00185	2.3150	1.4949	.8650	27.83	557.0		26.63	189.2		
	.00128	2.3040	1.4950	.8646	27.55	578.0		26.54	195.3		
Lead oleate	.00152	2.2890	1.4937	.8684	27.36	368.42		26.48	181.58		
	.00102	2.2849	1.4938	.8668	27.26	431.40	504c.c	26.43	127.45	126.88	4.29D
	.00074	2.2829	1.4939	.8656	27.17	459.46		26.40	121.62		

oleates. Unfortunately, however, we did not meet with much success as both these oleates were found to be too insoluble in the common solvents to admit of direct dipole

moment measurement. We have, however, lately obviated the above difficulty by using benzene-alcohol mixture as the solvent and applying Guggenheim's method of calculation, the results of which would constitute a future publication.

It will be noted that (from Table I) of the six soaps, the P_2 versus f_2 curves show the usual positive slopes for all soaps except that of calcium and lead which latter show negative slope. In other words, the latter soaps are more polar in dilute solution. It is believed that this behaviour is at least in part caused by the strong association tendency of these soap molecules to form micelles at higher concentration.

Of the transition elements, we have studied nickel and copper oleate. It will be observed from the figure that nickel has a fairly high dipole moment, 2.67 D and copper oleate has got somewhat less moment, 1.20 D , but has a value higher than its right hand neighbour, zinc. It is quite surprising that these substances, which are so highly soluble in hydrocarbon solvents, have such high dipole moments.

The question of geometry and polarity of the molecule naturally arises in connection with the dipole moment. For example, if the bivalent oleates have completely symmetrical structures, it is difficult to see how they give rise to such high moments at all. From these values we would suggest that the structure of these oleates is not symmetrical, the two valencies not being distributed in opposition to each other so as to annul the effect of each other. Further, it is quite likely that pseudo rings are formed as shown below by each of the fatty acids and these two rings by the exercise of co-ordinate valency between the two oxygen atoms and the central copper atom may not lie in the same plane. The most plausible disposition would be the four oxygen atoms tetrahedrally arranged round the copper atom.

The metallic soaps, for example, the nickel and copper oleates, have a very high solubility in hydrocarbon solvents and these solutions do not conduct current. From these it is generally assumed that these metallic soaps are non-polar compounds. In fact, there is no doubt from chemical standpoint that the bond between copper and the organic radical should be weakly ionic, if at all. The dipole moment data are, however, inconsistent with these chemical evidences. These two views can be reconciled if we postulate that the centre of negative charge of these metallic soaps must reside well inside the hydrocarbon part of the molecule. In fact, we may conceive that the negative charge in the oleate anion is distributed over the whole ion so that the centre of gravity of the charge lies further from copper which might explain the high dipole moment though the polarity of the bond may not be so high, since dipole moment involves the product of two quantities, charge and their separation. The mechanism of the distribution of the negative charge is probably a simple inductive effect. The negative charge of the $-\text{COO}^-$ end will polarise each of the $\text{C}-\text{H}$ bond by repulsion of the electrons, the more, the nearer the carbon atom, and this will in effect make the negative charge distributed over the whole hydrocarbon radical of the soap molecule.

Since the polarity of the metal-organic bond is caused by a displacement of the two valency electrons from the metal to the oleic acid radical, it seems reasonable that the dipole moment values will follow inversely the ionisation potential of the metal *i.e.*, if the energy required for the reaction,

is low, the dipole moment will be high and *vice versa*. This correlationship of course will not exist for salts of lower acids because the molecules being small, specific electrical disturbances will tend to mask such a relationship. In the following table have been compiled the values of the observed dipole moments and ionisation potentials. (taken from International Critical Tables). It will be observed that the expected relationship exists at least qualitatively among the elements of the same group of the periodic table (Group II). Copper and lead which belong to a different group (Group I), however, do not exactly fit in the above series. Only more work can show whether this inverse parallelism is mere accidental or not.

TABLE II

Soap.	Dipole moment.	Ionisation potential $M \longrightarrow M^{++} + 2e$.
Calcium oleate	4.49 D	17.91 volts
Magnesium oleate	1.66	22.58
Zinc oleate	0.29	27.25

Jatkar's New Equation.—Following an essentially Debye's method of calculation but with some imposed quantum restrictions on orientation of the dipoles in the electric field, Jatkar, Iyengar and Sathe (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1946, 28A, Part II, 1) have recently developed a new equation to replace Debye's equation. These authors claim superiority of their equation on various points of which they mention that the concentration variation of P_2 values will be smaller or negligible. We have recalculated all our values using this new equation and the μ -values are given in Table IV. These new μ -values, as found by Jatkar and his associates, are somewhat less than the Debye's value, and our calculations also show this to be so. This new equation by the above authors is

$$P = \frac{(\epsilon - 1)M}{d}$$

$$\text{Electronic polarisation} \quad P_e = \frac{(\pi^2 - 1)}{d}$$

$$P_{12} = \frac{(\epsilon - 1)(M_1 f_1 + M_2 f_2)}{d_{12}} = P_1 f_1 + P_2 f_2 \text{ and}$$

$$P_2 - P_e = \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{kT}$$

TABLE III

Dipole moments by Guggenheim's methods

Sample.	C (moles/c.c.).	$\epsilon - n^2$.	Δ .	Δ/C .	$(\Delta/C)c \rightarrow 0$.	μ .
Zinc oleate	2.253×10^{-6}	0.0426	0.0082	3.640×10^3	0	0
	7.656×10^{-6}	.0388	.0044	2.657×10^3		
	1.374×10^{-5}	.0370	.0026	1.980×10^3		
	0	.0344				
Copper oleate	3.938×10^{-6}	.0499	.0164	4.164×10^3	1.72×10^3	1.18×10^{-18}
	2.798×10^{-6}	.0436	.0101	3.609×10^3		
	1.940×10^{-6}	.0393	.0058	2.980×10^3		
	1.402×10^{-6}	.0370	.0035	2.497×10^3		
Magnesium oleate	3.287×10^{-6}	.0572	.0228	6.94×10^3	2.40×10^3	1.60×10^{-18}
	2.170×10^{-6}	.0459	.0115	5.30×10^3		
	1.517×10^{-6}	.0416	.0072	4.75×10^3		
	1.057×10^{-6}	.0383	.0039	3.70×10^3		
Nickel oleate	7.268×10^{-6}	.0862	.0488	14.930×10^3	5.9×10^3	2.19×10^{-18}
	2.266×10^{-6}	.0639	.0265	11.690×10^3		
	1.666×10^{-6}	.0540	.0166	9.963×10^3		
	1.113×10^{-6}	.0470	.0096	8.626×10^3		
Lead oleate	1.672×10^{-6}	.0579	.0205	12.27×10^3	19.8×10^3	4.01×10^{-18}
	1.125×10^{-6}	.0535	.0161	14.31×10^3		
	0.823×10^{-6}	.0512	.0138	15.92×10^3		
	0	.0374				
Calcium oleate	4.071×10^{-6}	.1019	.0684	16.80×10^3	29.3×10^3	4.873×10^{-18}
	2.863×10^{-6}	.0916	.0581	20.30×10^3		
	2.024×10^{-6}	.0813	.0468	23.12×10^3		
	1.411×10^{-6}	.0690	.0355	25.16×10^3		
0	.0335					

TABLE IV

Sample.	μ (Debye).	μ (Guggenheim).	μ (Statkar).
Zinc oleate	0.29 D	0 D	0.22 D
Copper oleate	1.20	1.18	1.07
Magnesium oleate	1.66	1.60	1.39
Nickel oleate	2.67	2.19	2.34
Lead oleate	4.29	4.01	3.22
Calcium oleate	4.49	4.87	3.78

As far as our data go, this new equation is not found to offer any advantage or disadvantage over the classical Debye equation, the variation of P_2 with concentration being of the same order, if not more, with this new equation as that obtained from the classical equation.

Guggenheim's Method of Calculation.—Very recently Guggenheim (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1949, **45**, 714) has proposed a simple and straight forward method of calculating μ . His method requires very accurate dielectric constant and refractive index values but requires only density values of ordinary accuracy. This is a great experimental advantage in working with volatile solvents. Guggenheim's method consists in finding the slope of the $\epsilon - n^2$ versus C (moles per c.c.) curve which should be a straight line if the mixture laws for refractivity and polarisation are valid. This slope is equated to the following expression

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{(\epsilon_0 + 2)(n_0^2 + 2)}{3} \cdot \frac{4\pi N}{3} \cdot \frac{\mu^2}{3kT}$$

$$\text{i.e., } \mu_{\text{Guggenheim}} = 0.0127 \sqrt{\frac{3T \times \text{slope}}{(\epsilon_0 + 2)(n_0^2 + 2)}} \times 10^{-18}$$

Evidently, the intercept of the above curve on the y -axis would be equal to $\epsilon_0 - n_0^2$ and so would be the same for all solutes in the same solvent. In attempting to apply this method to our data we find that the points fall fairly well on a straight line having a common intercept at the actually observed value of $\epsilon_0 - n_0^2$. There is, however, much uncertainty in finding the slope and to obviate the uncertainty of finding the slope we have, following Guggenheim, first calculated Δ as given below. Next Δ/C is plotted against C and extrapolated $C=0$. μ is then calculated from the equation given below:

$$\Delta = (\epsilon - n^2) - (\epsilon_0 - n_0^2)$$

$$\mu = 0.0127 \times 10^{-18} \sqrt{\frac{3T(\Delta/C)_{C=0}}{(\epsilon_0 + 2)(n_0^2 + 2)}}$$

The results of our calculation are presented in Table III and a comparison is made with μ , calculated, by Debye's method, in Table IV. We have found that much labour in calculation is saved by using Guggenheim's method. It is further to be pointed out that since each point on the graph is based on both dielectric constant and refractive index, the errors in both have more chance to cancel out from the final result, whereas in Debye's method of calculation differences of two large quantities, viz., $P_{12} - P_{1f_1}$ and $(P_2)_\infty - (R_2)_\infty$ are involved introducing uncertainty in the final result.

It will be observed that the agreement between μ_{Debye} and $\mu_{\text{Guggenheim}}$ is fairly good for all soaps except those of lead and calcium. Perhaps the larger extrapolation needed for these two soaps and also their anomalous concentration variation of polarisation, as already pointed out, may contribute to this larger difference.

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